

Bistatic Aspect Diversity for Improved SAR Target Recognition

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Abstract — This paper analyzes the potential for improvement in the performance of automatic target recognition (ATR) for synthetic-aperture radar (SAR) with bistatic aspect diversity. Initial assessments using decision-level fusion of monostatic observations with bistatic observations provide promising results. Data was generated using three civilian vehicle facet files and an electromagnetic scattering simulator. Classification was performed using normalized cross-correlation template matching and majority voting. Results showed an increase in the probability of correct classification with decision-level fusion of bistatic observations over classification using single observations.

Keywords – automatic target recognition, aspect diversity, bistatic radar, synthetic aperture radar

I. INTRODUCTION

Synthetic-aperture radar (SAR) is a popular surveillance mode due to its ability to image environments in a wide variety of weather and lighting conditions. Despite its versatility, however, SAR images tend to be plagued by a speckled texture, are monochromatic, and offer less detail than other imaging systems [1], making recognition of targets in SAR images a challenging task. As a result, an extensive amount of research has been performed in the area of SAR automatic target recognition (ATR). A recent branch of SAR ATR research has led to the investigation of *bistatic* SAR ATR [2,3]. Bistatic radar, in general, has taken on new interest recently due to its ability to separate transmitting and receiving platforms. This separation allows the receiving platform to remain passive and covert and provides the ability to use transmitters of opportunity [4].

Another branch of SAR ATR research has led to the use of aspect diversity for improving target recognition [5-8]. The approaches fuse monostatic SAR observations of a target from multiple look angles to provide more information about the target and thereby improve recognition. Ruohong et al [5] have investigated data-level fusion using principal components analysis (PCA) and discrete wavelet transforms (DWT) to fuse multi-aspect target data. Jin et al [6] also investigated the use of PCA for data-level fusion, but noted that if the correlation between input images is low, that PCA will not preserve the fine details of the target. Brendel and Horowitz [7] fused observations at the image level by concatenating images for different look angles together, while Bhanu and

Jones [8] fused observations at the decision level with a majority voting scheme.

The work in this paper extends the concept of aspect diversity for SAR ATR from the monostatic domain to the bistatic domain. Rather than fuse observations from multiple monostatic look angles, the transmitter is kept in one location and multiple “views” of the target are acquired by moving the receiver platform (thereby changing the bistatic angle). The amount of new information that can be gained from successive bistatic observations is dependent on the correlation between the bistatic observation and the initial monostatic observation; with higher degrees of decorrelation implying greater information gains.

The analysis approach described above will serve as an initial assessment of the potential for SAR ATR performance improvement through bistatic aspect diversity. Consequentially, the scope of this paper is limited to scenarios where the elevation of the transmitter and receiver is constant, and where the transmitter aperture is centered at 0° azimuth. Measurement noise is assumed to be additive Gaussian and targets are assumed to be perfectly registered. Empirical analysis is performed using data generated by an electromagnetic scattering simulator that makes assumptions about the target environment and the targets themselves. These assumptions are outlined in Section II. The results of this initial investigation indicate value in future, broader, investigation of the benefits of bistatic aspect diversity in SAR ATR.

An outline of the remainder of this paper is as follows. Section II addresses the data used for empirical analysis and the EM scattering simulator used to generate them. Section III examines the relationship between bistatic angle and the rate at which bistatic observations decorrelate relative to a monostatic observation. Descriptions of the template matching classification method and majority voting decision fusion scheme are outlined in Section IV. Section V presents the results of this investigation and Section VI concludes with a discussion and plans for future research.

II. DATA GENERATION

Currently, non-military bistatic SAR datasets are scarce, and the time and monetary cost of generating new real-world datasets is prohibitive. As a result, an electromagnetic (EM) scattering simulator was employed to generate the data for the experiments outlined in this paper. In addition to being easily accessible and low-cost, synthetic data also allows complete control over experiments and the ability to eliminate extraneous variables such as clutter, interference, and measurement imperfections. A bistatic extension of the monostatic EM scattering simulator outlined in [9], ‘‘Raider Tracer,’’ was chosen as the EM simulator for this paper, due to its availability and relative ease of use.

Raider Tracer is a physical optics (PO)-based RF prediction script written in MATLAB that simulates the far-field scattering response of a given target facet model to a bistatic (and monostatic for a bistatic angle of zero) radar. The simulator assumes that the target is in the far-field and that all facets are perfect electrical conductors (PEC). It excludes the effects of diffraction and polarization. Users provide the target facet model, the number of bounces collected for each simulated ray, and lists of the frequencies and azimuth-elevation angle pairs to be used in the simulation. The simulated response is a two-dimensional complex-valued matrix indexed by frequency and azimuth-elevation angle pair [9].

Fig. 1. Overhead views (top row) and rotated side views (bottom row) of the faceted civilian vehicle target models used to generate simulated bistatic SAR scattering responses: Nissan Maxima (left), Toyota Camry (center), and Toyota Tacoma (right).

Three civilian vehicle facet files serve as targets for the experiments in this paper: a Nissan Maxima, a Toyota Camry, and a Toyota Tacoma. Visualizations of these models can be seen in Fig. 1. All three targets have the same orientation relative to the bistatic SAR geometry. They are positioned so that the ground plane is the x-y plane, and the center of the car is at (0,0). All three vehicles point in the positive-x direction.

Fig. 2. Overhead views of the bistatic geometry for two experiments. Views show azimuth only (elevation is constant throughout time and experiments). The bistatic angle, β , is altered each experiment so that the transmitter remains in the same location (centered at 0°) and the receiver is β° away from the transmitter.

The elevations of both the transmitter and receiver remain constant, both throughout the experiments, and with respect to slow time, such that $\theta_t(\tau) = \theta_r(\tau) = 30^\circ \forall \tau$ for each experiment. The azimuth angle traversed by each platform for each experiment is $\Delta\phi_t = \Delta\phi_r = 3^\circ$ so that the bistatic angle, β , remains constant with respect to slow time throughout a single experiment. The work outlined in this paper seeks to analyze the benefits to ATR performance of adding bistatic SAR observations from multiple receiver locations with the same, single, transmitter. As such, the transmitter aperture center is kept constant at 0° for all experiments and the bistatic angle is altered in each experiment so that the receiver azimuth is $\phi_r(\tau) = \phi_t(\tau) + \beta$, where $\phi_t \in [-1.5^\circ, 1.5^\circ]$. Geometries for two example experiments can be seen in Fig 2. Note that bistatic angle remains constant within a single scenario, but changes from experiment to experiment.

Bandwidth is kept constant at $B = 500\text{MHz}$. Range resolution is dependent on the bistatic angle and bandwidth and is calculated as

$$\delta_r = \frac{c}{2B\cos(\beta/2)}, \quad (1)$$

where c is the speed of light [2]. For a constant bandwidth and increasing bistatic angle between 0° and 90° , the range resolution increases exponentially with respect to β . For the experiments in this paper, the smallest range resolution is $\delta_r = 0.3\text{m}$ when $\beta = 0^\circ$ and the largest is $\delta_r = 0.44\text{m}$ when $\beta = 90^\circ$.

Fig. 3. Images formed using the bistatic backprojection algorithm (BPA) and the scattering responses simulated by Raider Tracer. Images are of the Toyota Camry (top row), Nissan Maxima (middle row) and Toyota Tacoma (bottom row) for the monostatic case (left), a bistatic angle of $\beta = 10^\circ$ (center), a bistatic angle of $\beta = 20^\circ$ (right), and the aforementioned simulation parameters. Images are shown in a dB scale.

Frequency is simulated over the range $f \in [f_c - B/2, f_c + B/2]$ where the center frequency is $f_c = 10\text{GHz}$. Both the frequency range and transmitter-receiver locations are sampled $N = 256$ times over the duration of the simulation. With a range resolution of $\delta_r = 0.3\text{m}$, the range extent is $256 \cdot 0.3\text{m} = 76.8\text{m}$.

Sidelobes are suppressed using Taylor weighting with a peak sidelobe level relative to the mainlobe peak of -35dB . Images are formed using the bistatic backprojection algorithm (BPA) and an oversampling factor of eight [4]. Pixel size is defined as 0.15m (half of the range resolution) and the image size is defined as $8.1\text{m} \times 8.1\text{m}$ ($54\text{ pixels} \times 54\text{ pixels}$). Example images of the three targets at three different bistatic angles can be seen in Fig. 3.

III. CORRELATION OF OBSERVATIONS

Normalized circular cross-correlation (NCCC) is used for two purposes in this paper. First, cross-correlation indicates the amount of shared information between a monostatic image of a target and a bistatic image of the same target for varying bistatic angle. Second, NCCC is used for template-matching classification. It is assumed that there is sufficient white space around the targets such that circular cross-correlation is equivalent to cross-correlation (while retaining the efficiency of FFT implementation). Normalized circular cross-correlation is calculated as follows. Images are normalized to have zero mean and unit variance before cross-correlation. Circular cross-correlation is implemented using the two-dimensional Fast Fourier Transform (2-D FFT) so that the cross-correlation, C_{AB} , between two normalized images, A and B , is

$$C_{AB} = \mathcal{F}_2^{-1}\{\mathcal{F}_2\{A\} \cdot [\mathcal{F}_2\{B\}]^*\} \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{F}_2 is the 2-D Discrete Fourier Transform and \mathcal{F}_2^{-1} is the 2-D Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform. The cross-correlation image, C_{AB} , is normalized so that the autocorrelation at zero lag is identically 1.0.

The normalized cross-correlation coefficient is calculated between the complex monostatic image of a target and the complex bistatic image of the same target for bistatic angles between $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = 90^\circ$ at 1° intervals. All of the images used contain no added noise. The normalized cross-correlation coefficient is simply the normalized cross-correlation from (2) for zero lag, or $C_{AB}(0,0)$.

Fig. 4. Magnitude of the normalized cross-correlation coefficient calculated between the complex image of the target at $\beta = 0^\circ$ (monostatic case) and the complex image of the target at $\beta > 0^\circ$ (bistatic cases) versus β for $\beta \in [0^\circ, 90^\circ]$.

A plot of the magnitude of the normalized cross-correlation coefficient for each target versus bistatic angle can be seen in Fig. 4. From the plot, one can see that a monostatic image of a target and a bistatic image of the same target are essentially completely uncorrelated for bistatic angles of $\beta > 4^\circ$ (when the transmitting and receiving apertures no longer overlap). However, there are a few spikes in correlation (or negative correlation) around $\beta \approx 13^\circ$, $\beta \approx 43^\circ$ and $\beta \approx 70^\circ$. These spikes, however, are still relatively low compared to the correlation associated with small bistatic angles.

Fig. 5. Normalized cross-correlation coefficient calculated between the magnitude image of the target at $\beta = 0^\circ$ (monostatic case) and the magnitude image of the target at $\beta > 0^\circ$ (bistatic cases) versus β for $\beta \in [0^\circ, 90^\circ]$.

A plot of the normalized cross-correlation coefficient for the magnitude image of each target versus bistatic angle can be seen in Fig. 5. This plot shows a more gradual decay in correlation with respect to bistatic angle, with the exception of a few large peaks in correlation for the Maxima target around $\beta \approx 45^\circ$ and $\beta \approx 67^\circ$. However, it is still evident that correlation is much higher when the transmitting and receiving apertures overlap.

This cross-correlation analysis demonstrates the utility of bistatic SAR aspect diversity for improved ATR accuracy. Even for small bistatic angles, bistatic images are highly uncorrelated with a monostatic image of the same target, and therefore contain additional information about the target. As ATR accuracy is directly related to amount of available information about the target, this increase in information indicates the added value of bistatic observations.

IV. AUTOMATIC TARGET RECOGNITION

A simple template-matching classifier is implemented in order to evaluate the ATR benefit of adding bistatic observations to a monostatic observation. The classifier is first applied to individual observations for each bistatic angle ($\beta \in [0^\circ, 60^\circ]$) over a series of Monte Carlo simulations to estimate the probability of correct classification, p , when using a bistatic angle on its own (without fusion). Following that, a majority voting scheme is executed to fuse the classifier decisions of a selected number of observations and the probability of correct classification for the augmented data set is estimated.

A. Preprocessing

Prior to template matching, the raw complex-valued images are converted into logarithmic magnitude images so that each image is real and in the dB scale. Next the images are normalized by subtracting the sample mean and dividing by the sample standard deviation so that all of the images have zero mean and unit variance.

B. Template Matching

Template matching is performed at each bistatic angle by comparing a test image to templates of the three target classes and selecting the class that is a best match for the test image. The original, non-noisy, images of the three targets at each bistatic angle serve as templates for the test images at the corresponding bistatic angle and it is assumed that the correct bistatic angle is known. A 'best match' is determined using normalized cross-correlation, where the correlation coefficient between a test image and each template is calculated using (3). The most likely target class is selected to be the class corresponding to the template which maximizes the normalized correlation coefficient. The probability of correct classification is estimated as the number of correct detections divided by the number of test images.

C. Majority Voting

In [10], Lam and Suen analyze the application of majority voting to pattern recognition. They cite a study in [11] that compared five decision-level fusion strategies (majority vote, Bayesian, logistic regression, fuzzy integral, and neural network) and found that while simple,

a majority vote performs just as well as its more-complicated counterparts. This is intuitive in that an incorrect classification requires the majority of voters to not only provide an incorrect classification, but to provide the *same* incorrect classification. Assuming that the voters are all reliable (they each have a probability of correct classification of $p > 0.5$), the probability that the majority of voters will make the same error decreases with the number of voters.

Lam and Suen address scenarios for an even number of voters and an odd number of voters. An even number of voters presents the possibility of a tie for a binary class and therefore a "rejection" of a test sample. For the purposes of the work in this paper, only an odd number of voters is examined. For n (where n is odd) voters, at least $k = (n + 1)/2$ voters must agree. For the case where all voters have the *same* probability of being correct, p , the probability of the consensus being correct, P_C , is based on the binomial distribution and is calculated as

$$P_C(n) = \sum_{m=k}^n \binom{n}{m} p^m (1-p)^{n-m}. \quad (3)$$

[10]. The authors extend this definition to analyze the effect of adding two votes to an odd number of votes when the probability of being correct is *different* for each voter. Assume that the original voters each have a different probability of being correct, p_i . Two voters are added to the pool and each have a probability of being correct of q_1 and q_2 . The probability of the consensus being correct increases if the odds ratios for the new voters satisfy the inequality

$$\frac{q_1 q_2}{(1-q_1)(1-q_2)} > \frac{p_i}{(1-p_i)} \text{ for all } i. \quad (4)$$

[Lam]. In other words, the odds ratio of the new voters must be larger than the odds ratio associated with the original voter with the largest probability of being correct.

Fig. 6. Decision curves for adding two additional voters to an odd number of voters. Lines indicate the probability of correct classification curve when the highest probability of correct classification in the original pool is p_i . In order for the probability of the consensus being correct, P_C , to increase, the two new voters must be selected so that the point (q_1, q_2) falls above the line for p_i .

If p_{max} is the largest probability of being correct for the n initial voters, then (4) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{q_1 q_2}{(1 - q_1)(1 - q_2)} > \frac{p_{max}}{(1 - p_{max})}. \quad (5)$$

Fig. 9 shows the relationship between q_1 and q_2 for various values of p_{max} . Each line in the plot indicates the probability of correct classification curve when the highest probability of correct classification in the original pool is p_i . In order for P_C to increase, the two new voters must be selected so that the point (q_1, q_2) falls above the line for p_i . Thus, decision-level fusion via majority voting of a monostatic observation with two additional bistatic observations will increase the overall probability of correct classification if and only if the probabilities of correct classification satisfy (5).

For the purposes of this paper, assume that the initial number of voters is $n = 1$ (where the single vote is based on the monostatic observation) and that its probability of being correct is p_{mono} . Two new voters (two bistatic look angles) are added to the voting pool with probabilities of being correct: $p_{\beta 1}$ and $p_{\beta 2}$. From Fig. 6, one can see that even if $p_{\beta 1}$ and $p_{\beta 2}$ are both lower than p_{mono} , the probability of a the consensus being correct, P_C , may still be greater than p_{mono} , if they satisfy (5). As an example, assume $p_{mono} = 0.8$, $p_{\beta 1} = 0.75$ and $p_{\beta 2} = 0.7$, then the ratio inequality is $(0.75 \cdot 0.7)/(0.25 \cdot 0.3) = 7 > 0.8/0.2 = 4$ is satisfied, and P_C will increase.

V. RESULTS

The effects of bistatic azimuth diversity on automatic target recognition are evaluated empirically for the three civilian vehicles targets: a Nissan Maxima, a Toyota Camry, and a Toyota Tacoma. Test data were generated using the EM scattering simulator, Raider Tracer, described in Section II.

Fig. 7. Two noisy images of the Tacoma vehicle at $\beta = 0^\circ$ (monostatic). Noise was added to the complex phase history data to achieve a signal-to-noise ratio of $SNR = -40dB$ ($SNR = 8.16dB$ in the image domain). The back-projection algorithm has a low-pass filter effect on the AWGN noise in the image domain. Images are shown in a dB scale.

For testing purposes, 500 noisy test images were generated for each target at each bistatic angle, with ϕ_t fixed at 0° . Noise was added in the phase history domain to achieve a signal-to-noise ratio of $SNR = -40dB$ ($SNR = 8.16dB$ in the image domain) for all three targets for each bistatic angle. Two example noisy images of the

Tacoma target (illuminated by a monostatic system) can be seen in Fig. 7.

In order to establish an improvement in ATR via azimuth diversity, a baseline assessment of ATR for single, non-fused, look angles is performed. Classification is executed on the 1500 images (500 for each target) for each bistatic angle, individually. A confusion matrix and the probability of correct classification are calculated for each bistatic angle.

		$\beta = 0^\circ$		
		Target		
Class	Maxima	0.5560	0.0560	0.3880
	Camry	0.1160	0.7660	0.1180
	Tacoma	0.3180	0.0460	0.6360
Est. probability of correct classification		p = 0.6527		

		$\beta = 8^\circ$		
		Target		
Class	Maxima	0.6980	0.2040	0.0980
	Camry	0.4180	0.4200	0.1620
	Tacoma	0.1800	0.1520	0.6680
Est. probability of correct classification		p = 0.5953		

		$\beta = 20^\circ$		
		Target		
Class	Maxima	0.7240	0.1320	0.1440
	Camry	0.1200	0.6480	0.2320
	Tacoma	0.1300	0.2620	0.6080
Est. probability of correct classification		p = 0.6600		

Table 1. Confusion matrices for classification of images with a bistatic angle of $\beta = 0^\circ$, $\beta = 8^\circ$, and $\beta = 20^\circ$. Columns represent the accurate class of the target, and rows represent the class selected by the classifier.

Fig. 8. Estimates of the probability of correct classification versus bistatic angle when a single perspective is used for classification. Estimates are based on the classification of 1500 images (500 of each civilian target).

Three example confusion matrices for $\beta = 0^\circ$, $\beta = 8^\circ$ and $\beta = 20^\circ$ can be seen in Table 1 and a stem plot of the estimated probability of correct classification versus bistatic angle when a single perspective is used can be seen in Fig. 8. The inequality established in (5) is satisfied for

any pair of bistatic observations shown in Fig. 8. This means that the overall probability of correct classification will improve if the monostatic observation is augmented by any two of the bistatic observations. To demonstrate this empirically, majority voting is applied to the set of voters: $\beta = 0^\circ$ (monostatic), $\beta = 8^\circ$, and $\beta = 20^\circ$. Bistatic observations with relatively low probabilities of correct classification are intentionally chosen to demonstrate that improvement in ATR can be gained even for poor bistatic observations.

		Target		
		Maxima	Camry	Tacoma
Class	Maxima	0.6580	0.0280	0.1680
	Camry	0.0120	0.8680	0.0100
	Tacoma	0.2280	0.0300	0.7580
Est. probability of correct classification		p = 0.7613		

Table 2. Confusion matrix for normalized cross-correlation classification with majority voting. Voting fuses observations at $\beta = 0^\circ$ (monostatic), $\beta = 8^\circ$, and $\beta = 20^\circ$. Columns represent the accurate class of the target, and rows represent the class selected by the classifier.

The confusion matrix for normalized correlation classification with majority voting using three observations ($\beta = 0^\circ$, $\beta = 8^\circ$, and $\beta = 20^\circ$) can be seen in Table 2. The results of majority voting classification show a marked improvement over classification with a single, monostatic, observation. This confirms the expectations set by (5). Any two bistatic observations would also produce an improved probability of correct classification for the consensus, P_C , and P_C would increase even more if the bistatic observations were chosen to maximize the individual probabilities of correct classification, p_i . Additionally, as (3) suggests, P_C could be further increased by increasing the number of reliable voters.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a novel ATR method that exploits aspect-diverse bistatic SAR images via majority voting decision fusion. Correlation of bistatic images of a target with a monostatic image of the same target demonstrates the unique information that additional bistatic observations contribute to a classifier. An initial assessment using a template-matching classifier, majority voting decision fusion, and three aspect-diverse observations yields encouraging results. Results showed an increase in the estimated probability of correct classification with decision-level fusion of bistatic observations over classification using single observations.

Future work will entail implementing additional classification methods, investigating ideal monostatic platform placement, and quantifying the performance benefits of additional bistatic observations as a function of bistatic angle. Additionally, tangential work, [12], has been performed in the area of image registration for bistatic aspect-diverse SAR images. Future work may combine these two research avenues and examine the trade-off between ATR benefits and registration degradation as a function of bistatic angle.

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